

Too sharp to handle: Unpleasantness from spiky object geometry in vision and touch

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Abstract. Humans tend to favor curved objects over sharp counterparts, yet little is known about how fine-grained geometric properties of angular surfaces influence affective evaluation across sensory modalities. We investigated how spike density, height, and thickness shape unpleasantness using 12 systematically varied 3D-printed spiky surfaces. Participants evaluated the unpleasantness under haptic, visual, and visuo-haptic conditions. Linear mixed models showed that sparser, higher, and thinner spikes felt more unpleasant, with stronger effects when touch was involved. These findings demonstrate that local geometric features systematically shape feelings of the surfaces and inform the design of tactile cues and expressive haptic interfaces.

Keywords: Affective touch · Unpleasantness · Surface · Vision.

1 Introduction

Humans tend to favor curved objects over sharp counterparts, with angular geometries often perceived as less pleasant across sensory modalities [1, 2]. Prior work has largely focused on global shape differences (e.g., curved vs. angular contours [3, 4, 5]), demonstrating that geometric features systematically influence affective evaluation. While visual studies have shown consistent preferences for curved over angular shapes [1], far less is known about how local geometric properties of surfaces influence affective responses through touch. In everyday interactions, visual and haptic information jointly contribute to evaluating object properties, yet the role of fine-grained geometric parameters such as spike density, height, and thickness remains poorly understood. Here, we systematically manipulate these parameters in controlled spiky surfaces and examine how they influence the feeling of unpleasantness across visual, haptic, and visuohaptic modalities.

2 Methods

27 participants ($M_{\text{age}} = 25.4$, $SD = 5.31$, 9 males, 1 diverse) took part in the study following local ethics approval (2022-003). We employed a within-

participants design with three modality conditions (haptic, visual, visuo-haptic), counterbalanced across individuals.

Participants evaluated 12 3D-printed spiky objects (Objet 30 Pro, Stratasys Ltd., Fig. 1) in which one geometric parameter was systematically varied at a time: spike distance (6.1, 9, 15, 18 mm), thickness (bottom/base radius: 2, 4, 5, 5.9 mm), and height (tip height/tip radius: 4, 10, 13, 17 mm). In the haptic condition, participants explored the objects with their dominant hand while vision was blocked; in the visual condition, objects were inspected without touch; in the visuo-haptic condition, both modalities were available. Each object was explored for 4 seconds and rated for unpleasantness on a 7-point Likert scale (1: *very pleasant*, 7: *very unpleasant*). During haptic and visuo-haptic exploration, contact force was recorded to control for potential effects of pressure (load cell: KD60-80; amplifier: GSV-6K, both ME-Systeme Germany), and digitized using a National Instruments data acquisition system (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Illustration of the experimental setup (left) and geometrical parameters of the haptic stimuli (right).

Applied force did not significantly affect ratings ($M_{\text{force}} = 1.257$ N visuo-haptic; $M_{\text{force}} = 1.235$ N haptic) and was therefore not included in final analyses. Unpleasantness ratings were analyzed using linear mixed-effects models (*lme4* [6], *lmerTest* [7]) with geometry and modality as fixed effects and participant as a random intercept. Post-hoc comparisons used *emmeans* with Tukey correction.

3 Results

Fig. 2. Mean pleasantness as a function of spike properties - distance, height, and thickness - across haptic, visuo-haptic, and visual modalities. Higher values correspond to greater unpleasantness.

Density Model. There was a main effect of density, $F(3, 933.26) = 219.16$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .41$, but no main effect of modality, $F(2, 939.43) = 1.57$, $p = .209$. The interaction was significant, $F(6, 933.26) = 2.37$, $p = .028$, $\eta_p^2 = .02$. Unpleasantness increased as spike density decreased (all $p < .001$), with no difference between the two lowest densities (15 vs. 18 mm), demonstrating stronger effects for haptics than vision (Fig. 2).

Thickness Model. Thickness affected unpleasantness ($F(3, 933.38) = 232.43$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .43$), as did modality ($F(2, 940.45) = 13.33$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .03$). The interaction was significant: $F(6, 933.38) = 3.03$, $p = .006$, $\eta_p^2 = .02$. Thinner spikes were rated as more unpleasant across modalities (all $p < .001$), except the two thickest stimuli (5 vs. 5.9 mm; $p = .94$) in the visual condition (Fig. 2).

Height Model. Height influenced unpleasantness, $F(3, 933.09) = 7.99$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .03$, as did modality, $F(2, 938.60) = 6.70$, $p = .001$, $\eta_p^2 = .01$. The interaction was significant, $F(6, 933.09) = 2.40$, $p = .026$, $\eta_p^2 = .02$. The shortest spikes (4 mm) were rated as less unpleasant than taller spikes, primarily when visual information was available (Fig. 2).

4 Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange

Fine-grained geometry systematically shaped unpleasantness across visual, haptic, and visuo-haptic modalities. Thickness and density showed the strongest effects, highlighting the role of local structure in affective evaluation. Patterns were largely consistent across modalities, with touch often producing stronger unpleasantness, suggesting haptic exploration likely increases sensitivity to local geometric features such as sharp angles. Notably, maintaining a constant spike angle required varying base radius, complicating the interpretation of height effects.

The present findings suggest several directions for future research, including how additional geometric properties (e.g., curvature, symmetry, or orientation) contribute to affective surface perception. Geometric features rarely occur in isolation; their interaction with material properties (e.g., softness or temperature) may further influence unpleasantness. Understanding this combination could provide a more complete account of affective multisensory processing.

These findings inform research in haptics, product design, robotics, and human-computer interaction. Manipulating surface geometry may support affective tactile cues, for example, in safety signaling, assistive technologies, or expressive haptic feedback. Identifying how geometric parameters influence unpleasantness may help guide the multisensory interface design. We invite material scientists to discuss potential implications and future applications.

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